

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH TOURISM: A PATH OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH TOURISM: A PATH OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Dr. RAJKUMAR SHIVAJIRAO SARODE, Assistant Professor, DVVPPF's IBMRD, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra

Dr. NACHIKET VIJAY DEODHAR, Assistant Professor, DVVPPF's IBMRD, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra

Dr. SACHIN D.KHARDE, Assistant Professor, MBA, Amrutvahini College of Engineering, Sangamner, Maharashtra

Abstract

This article examines the evolution of women's empowerment and tourism integration, revealing an empowering journey that transcends regional boundaries. Focusing on economic development, she explains that tourism creates opportunities for women to directly participate in business life, provides economic independence and plays an important role in supporting family health. Additionally, this article covers entrepreneurship by showing how entrepreneurship supports women entrepreneurs and small businesses; challenges gender rights, and women action leaders and innovators in their communities. The main theme focused on improving skills and training, showing that participation in the tourism industry is a continuous process of varying skills. These skills not only improve work ability, but also increase confidence and support personal development. This definition expands the role of women in community development through the role of tourism, as women often contribute to programs that improve the entire community, creating an impact on local businesses and infrastructure. When women represent their communities, cultural change becomes a powerful tool for empowerment. This exchange not only provides a platform to share cultural heritage, but also breaks down stereotypes and encourages international participation. Finally, this chapter highlights the important role of tourism in paving the way to gender equality, envisioning a future in which women can participate in shaping their own destinies, leading in parallel to a lack of achievement in human civilization.

Keywords: Economic empowerment entrepreneurship skill development community upliftment cultural exchange.

Introduction

The combination of women's empowerment and tourism is like a beacon of hope in the world of economic development, a beacon for economic development and gender equality (Rajoana and Saxena, 2022). This intersection not only gives women the opportunity to become financially independent, but also to grow as individuals and in society. The interaction of these two factors creates a picture of change that demonstrates women's ability to be agents of change in their own lives and communities. Tourism transforms support into change, breaking down barriers and promoting a future where women actively control their own destinies (Freund and Hernandez-Maskivker, 2021). This article examines the many aspects of how tourism can empower women and have positive impacts on the region.

Economic Empowerment

The economic landscape of many countries grows with gender inequality, limiting women's employment and entrepreneurial opportunities (Laing and Frost, 2017). Tourism has become a transformative force by offering more opportunities to women (Ghadban, Kamar and Haidar, 2023). The hotel industry has become a major source of employment in tourist destinations around the world, providing women with jobs in hotels, restaurants, and other service industries (Susila, Harismah, Priyono, Setyawan, & Maulana, 2023). This participation in the workforce empowers women, providing them with income, financial independence, and the ability to contribute to the well-being of their families (Manfreda, Ye, and Nelson-Miles, 2023). In addition, women often find a place in many business-related sectors (Sedgley, Pritchard, Morgan, & Hanna, 2017). Women entrepreneurs are

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH TOURISM: A PATH OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

making their mark in the business world through handicrafts, local tourism or arts businesses (Nisbett, 2017). This company not only fosters human potential, but also breaks gender stereotypes by showing women how to work efficiently and effectively in business models that replicate their own communities (Fan, Wang, and Xiao, 2021)

Entrepreneurship and Small Businesses

The empowerment of women in tourism continues from traditional jobs to business and small businesses (McCall and Mearns, 2021). From boutique hotels to cultural tourism and handicraft markets, the business sector offers a conducive environment for women to establish and manage businesses (Vij, Upadhya, Agha, Begum, Kashmoola, & Senior, 2023). These businesses not only benefit the local economy, but also provide opportunities for women to break the glass ceiling and become community leaders and creators of the new (Pung, Yung, Khoo-Lattimore, & Del Chiappa, 2020). Women are becoming architects of economic change, disrupting the narrative of space and challenging the current status quo. Work done by women has a lot of impact on the economy, influences social beliefs, and encourages future women to find the best in their careers (Hillman and Radel, 2022).

Skill Development and Education

Participation in the business sector requires a wide range of skills, from language skills to customer service, business management and marketing (Hamid, Ali, Azhar, and Khan, 2021). In the business world, women are on the verge of endless skill development, and the acquired knowledge not only improves their working abilities but also enters their lives (Hao, Zhang, and Xiao, 2021). Women participating in the tourism sector, receiving training and improving their skills, and creating a productive support circle. New resources give them confidence and provide the tools they need to solve problems in their work and personal lives (Bagheri, Ghaderi, Abdi, & Hall, 2023). In this sense, tourism serves as an educational bridge that enables women to overcome obstacles and reach their potential (Uduji et al., 2017). 2021).

Community Development

When used correctly, tourism has the power to support entire communities. Women often play an important role in community tourism projects to ensure a fair distribution of benefits (Efthymiadou and Farmaki, 2023). Transferring tourism revenue into the local economy can help improve infrastructure, health, and education over a long period of time and create an environment conducive to growth (Abou-Shouk, Mannaa, and Elbaz, 2021). As community leaders, women carry out projects to protect culture and environmental justice. Women become architects of sustainable development by participating in the decision-making process of tourism, and the fact that tourism quality is not short-lived has a long-term impact on public health (Tucker, 2023).

Cultural Exchange and Empowerment

Tourism is a way of exchanging culture and understanding between different groups of people. Women are carriers of cultural heritage, representing their communities and sharing their traditions, stories and lifestyles with tourist tourism (Laing and Frost, 2017). This cultural exchange not only empowers women by allowing them to reveal their past, but also challenges preconceived notions and strengthens the response of the international community (Hassan and Damir, 2022). Through cultural exchange, women find voices beyond borders and create unmistakable connections. This support from the leadership of this culture helps break down barriers and create a world that respects diversity and recognizes women as people important to the richness of human progress (Nair and Segura, 2021).

Conclusion

The intersection of women's empowerment and tourism opens up a world of possibilities where travel transcends the physical boundaries of space and becomes transformative for women as a whole. As we explore the complex web of business support, entrepreneurship, skills development, community support and cultural exchange, it is clear that tourism rather than business tourism comes to the fore. To see a future where women participate in determining their own destiny, we must identify and support programs that use the potential of tourism to achieve gender equality. The stories of powerful women in the travel industry are more than personal achievements; they are the blueprint for a society in which all women can embark on a journey of self-discovery and empowerment, breaking out of the fabric of human progress forever.

References

1. Abou-Shouk, M. A., Mannaa, M. T., & Elbaz, A. M. (2021). Women's empowerment and tourism development: A cross-country study. *Tourism management perspectives*, 37, 100782.
2. Bagheri, F., Ghaderi, Z., Abdi, N., & Hall, C. M. (2023). Female entrepreneurship, creating shared value, and empowerment in tourism; the neutralizing effect of gender-based discrimination. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 26(21), 3465-3482.
3. Efthymiadou, F., & Farmaki, A. (2023). Women empowerment in tourism: progressing the research agenda. *Tourism Review*.
4. Fan, X., Wang, J., & Xiao, H. (2021). Women's travel in the Tang Dynasty: Gendered identity in a hierarchical society. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 89, 103231.
5. Freund, D., & Hernandez-Maskivker, G. (2021). Women managers in tourism: Associations for building a sustainable world. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 38, 100820.
6. Ghadban, S., Kamar, R., & Haidar, R. (2023). Decoding international Solo women travelers' experience: A qualitative analysis of user-generated videos. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 100648
7. Hamid, S., Ali, R., Azhar, M., & Khan, S. (2021). Solo travel and well-being amongst women: An exploratory study. *Indonesian Journal of Tourism and Leisure*, 2(1), 1-13.
8. Hao, F., Zhang, S., & Xiao, H. (2021). A return to innocence: Guimi tourism and women empowerment. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 23(6), 971-983.
9. Hillman, W., & Radel, K. (2022). Transformations of women in tourism work: A case study of emancipation in Nepal.
10. Hassan, S. B., & Damir, A. K. (2022). Sustainable Development and Gender Equality: Empowerment through Solo Female Travel Experiences. In *Planning and Managing Sustainability in Tourism: Empirical Studies, Best-practice Cases and Theoretical Insights* (pp. 187-203). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
11. Laing, J. H., & Frost, W. (2017). Journeys of well-being: Women's travel narratives of transformation and self-discovery in Italy. *Tourism Management*, 62, 110-119
12. Lionanda, G. (2023). Empowerment of Social Entrepreneurs for Women groups in Cultural Tourism Villages. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(4), 1068-1077.
13. Manfreda, A., Ye, I. Q., & Nelson-Miles, K. (2023). Transforming tourism's "field (work) of view". *Annals of Tourism Research*, 103, 103665.
14. McCall, C. E., & Mearns, K. F. (2021). Empowering women through community-based tourism in the Western Cape, South Africa. *Tourism Review International*, 25(2-3), 157-171.
15. Nair, B. B., & Segura, S. S. (2021). Tourism and sustainable development goal -5: A pathway for women's empowerment. 35(4), 19-31.
16. Nisbett, M. (2017). Empowering the empowered? Slum tourism and the depoliticization of poverty. *Geoforum*, 85, 37-45.
17. Pung, J. M., Yung, R., Khoo-Lattimore, C., & Del Chiappa, G. (2020). Transformative travel experiences and gender: A double duoethnography approach. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 23(5), 538-558. Rajoana, J., & Saxena, G. (2022). Role of Sundarbans bagh bidhwa entrepreneurs in tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 97, 103486

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH TOURISM: A PATH OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

18. Sedgley, D., Pritchard, A., Morgan, N., & Hanna, P. (2017). Tourism and autism: Journeys of mixed emotions. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 66, 14-25.
19. Susila, I, Harismah, K., Priyono, K. D., Setyawan, A. A., & Maulana, H. (2023). Does interconnectivity matter? An integration model of agro-tourism development. *Asia Pacific Management Review*.
20. Tucker, H. (2023). Gendering sustainability's contradictions: between change and continuity. In *Gender and Tourism Sustainability* (pp. 45-62). Routledge.
21. Vij, M., Upadhya, A., Agha, K., Begum, V., Kashmoola, B. W., & Senior, J. R. (2023). Female economic empowerment through tourism training in the United Arab Emirates. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 15(1), 18-28
22. Uduji, J. I., Okolo-Obasi, E. N., Onodugo, V. A., Nnabuko, J. O., & Adedibu, B. A. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and the role of rural women in strengthening agriculture-tourism linkages in Nigeria's oil producing communities. *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 19(6), 754-780.
23. Ranu Kumar, Kanika Mittal *Empowering Women Through Tourism: A Journey of Transformation Women Empowerment and Financial Literacy BOOK 2024*, (35 -38)